

1 Evaluation of a new approach for swine wastewater valorisation and treatment: a combined
2 system of ammonium recovery and aerated constructed wetland

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16 **HIGHLIGHTS**

- 17 • A combined ammonia stripping and aerated constructed wetlands system is evaluated at pilot
18 scale.
19 • 32% of ammonium nitrogen is recovered from swine wastewater by ammonia stripping
20 process.
21 • An alternative approach to biological nitrification-denitrification treatment is tested.
22 • Aerated constructed wetland nutrients and organic matter removals are higher than 80%.

23

24 **ABSTRACT**

25 Nitrate Vulnerable Zones (NVZs) are faced with a surplus of animal manure due to intensive
26 livestock production, and the high use of mineral nitrogen (N) fertilisers in crop production.
27 Recovery of N from animal manure to replace synthetic mineral fertilisers is considered a key
28 strategy to close the N loop for more sustainable agriculture and to meet strict legal frameworks.
29 In this study, N recovery from swine wastewater by an ammonia (NH₃) stripping process followed

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30 by purification via an aerated constructed wetland (ACW) was proposed as an alternative approach
 31 to conventional systems based on biological nitrification-denitrification (NDN) treatment. The
 32 performance of the NH_3 stripping pilot as well as the ACW was monitored in 2019-2020 over three
 33 periods, to evaluate the quality of recovered ammonium nitrate (AN) solution and the effluent of
 34 the ACW. Results showed that the NH_3 stripping unit recovered 21% of total-N (32% of mineral-
 35 N) in the form of AN solution. This could be used as a mineral fertiliser according to the criteria
 36 of the European Fertilising Products Regulation 2019/1009 and the technical proposal of manure-
 37 derived RENURE (REcovered Nitrogen from manURE) products by the European Joint Research
 38 Centre. As a RENURE product, AN solution would reach an end-of-manure status and could be
 39 used as a synthetic N fertiliser replacement. The tested ACW achieved a high removal efficiency
 40 with respect to suspended solids (96%), biological oxygen demand (96%), chemical oxygen
 41 demand (90%), total-N (80%), and total phosphorus (97%). The quality of ACW effluent was
 42 comparable to that of NDN treatment. Though the overall cost of the proposed pilot-scale process
 43 consisting of NH_3 stripping (5.1 € t^{-1}) and ACW (12 € t^{-1}) was calculated slightly higher than
 44 conventional NDN treatment (16 € t^{-1}), it is foreseen to outcompete at a higher loading rate (over
 45 $45 \text{ m}^3 \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$). Furthermore, post-purification will be needed for the ACW effluent to meet the
 46 requirements for discharge to surface water.

47 **KEYWORDS**

48 Animal manure, Wastewater treatment, Ammonia stripping, Aerated constructed wetland,
 49 RENURE

51 **GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT**

53 1. INTRODUCTION

54 Due to intensive livestock production, the region of Flanders (Belgium) has a nutrient surplus
55 available in the form of animal manure which cannot be applied directly on agricultural land as it
56 must comply with the Nitrates Directive (EU) 676/1991 application limit of 170 kg total nitrogen
57 (N) ha⁻¹ y⁻¹. Therefore, each year 3,700 kt of excess manure, containing 34 kt N, is treated by
58 different manure processing techniques such as biological treatment (i.e.,
59 nitrification/denitrification), anaerobic digestion (AD) and drying (VLM, 2020). Swine manure
60 accounts for around 70% of the total input of the Flemish manure processing and is mainly treated
61 by biological process, occasionally preceded by AD. During the biological wastewater treatment,
62 reduced N compounds are oxidized to nitrate (NO₃⁻) and subsequently removed as nitrogen gas
63 (N₂) through the nitrification-denitrification (NDN) pathway. As 0.035% of the N load is converted
64 into nitrous oxide (N₂O) during NDN (Kampschreur *et al.*, 2009), wastewater treatment contributes
65 almost 5% of the global N₂O emissions (Olivier *et al.*, 2017). Recent studies reported up to 0.78%
66 of N₂O losses during the treatment of NH₄-N-rich wastewaters (Wu *et al.*, 2014). In 2019, about
67 16 kt of N were converted into N₂ by biological manure treatment in Flanders (VLM, 2020). As
68 the nitrification of ammonium ions (NH₄⁺) to form NO₃⁻ requires oxidising power of oxygen, i.e.,
69 4.57 g O₂ per g of N oxidised (Magdum and Kalyanraman, 2017), oxygen-rich conditions must be
70 created. Thus, aeration is required resulting in an energy-demanding process. Meers *et al.* (2005;
71 2008) were the first to propose and subsequently successfully implement constructed wetland
72 (CW) systems for the post-treatment of biologically treated effluents towards dischargeable water.
73 This further increased the sustainability of biological treatment systems as it removed the need to
74 transport biologically treated effluents for spreading on land. Instead, the wetlands allowed in-situ
75 complete treatment from manure towards dischargeable water.

76
77 Although intensive livestock is producing surplus N that needs extra treatment, arable farming and
78 horticulture have an additional need for N in the form of mineral fertilisers, which are produced by
79 the energy-intensive Haber-Bosh process. Recovering N as a high-end product and recycling it as
80 mineral N fertiliser could help to overcome this paradoxical situation by reducing the N load in
81 manure processing installations, while partially replacing the demand for mineral fertilisers.
82 Alternative routes to conventional biological removal of N from swine wastewater can be classified
83 as membrane filtration and physicochemical processes. The advantage of such technologies is the

84 simultaneous removal of N, coupled with the production of biobased N fertilising products which
85 are gaining attention as replacements for synthetic mineral fertilisers (Zarebska *et al.*, 2015).
86 Ammonia (NH₃) stripping is a robust technology that usually requires simple pre-treatment. It is a
87 two-step process where in the first step NH₃ is transferred from the liquid effluent to the gas phase
88 (NH₃ stripping). Usually, this step takes place in a packed tower with an inert material to enhance
89 NH₃ removal. Subsequently, the gas phase enriched with NH₃ is washed with an acid solution to
90 recover NH₃ in the form of ammonium (NH₄) salts (NH₃ absorption). Sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄), nitric
91 acid (HNO₃), and gypsum (CaSO₄·2H₂O) have been recorded at full-scale NH₃ stripping
92 installations as washing agents. The use of H₂SO₄ or CaSO₄·2H₂O would result in ammonium
93 sulphate ((NH₄)₂SO₄) solutions, whereas the addition of HNO₃ would form ammonium nitrate
94 (NH₄NO₃, AN) solution (Brienza *et al.*, 2020). Compared to (NH₄)₂SO₄, AN contains twice the
95 amount of mineral N, thus representing a more interesting mineral N fertilising product (Sigurnjak
96 *et al.*, 2019). Recently, the Joint Research Centre (JRC) defined a set of criteria to define which
97 manure-derived products (RENURE products) could be applicable as mineral fertilisers in Nitrate
98 Vulnerable Zones (NVZs), adhering to the same regulations of synthetic fertilisers (Huygens *et al.*,
99 2020). Furthermore, the fertilisers' regulatory framework ascribes to the recently approved
100 Fertilising Products Regulation (FPR) (EU) 1009/2019, which includes manure-derived materials.
101 On the other hand, the reuse of NH₄ salts derived from NH₃ stripping in agriculture is hindered by
102 the Nitrates Directive, which restrains the application of N not only from animal manure but also
103 from manure-derived products (i.e., AN solution). As a result of this limitation, manure-surplus
104 regions (e.g., Flanders, Belgium) recourse to synthetic mineral fertilisers to meet crop N
105 requirements despite the availability of N in manure excess.

106
107 NH₃ stripping itself is not effective in removing other components such as organic matter (OM)
108 and phosphorus (P), thus its implementation for swine wastewater treatment should be
109 accompanied by other technologies. The constructed wetlands (CW) for wastewater treatment, also
110 known as treatment wetlands, are engineered systems designed and constructed to utilize natural
111 processes and remove pollutants from contaminated water within a more controlled environment.
112 CWs have been widely used for the treatment of various types of wastewater such as domestic
113 sewage, metallurgical, agricultural, swine manure, mine drainage, landfill leachate, urban runoff,
114 etc., worldwide (Donoso, 2018; Donoso *et al.*, 2019; Gupta *et al.*, 2020; Kadlec & Wallace, 2009;

115 Li et al., 2020; Maine et al., 2019; Maine et al., 2022; Nguyen et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2015, 2016;
116 Zhang et al., 2014). Yet, some of the constraints could be the low N and recalcitrant OM removal,
117 limited oxygen transfer, and the need for land availability. The effects of aeration and recirculation
118 on constructed wetlands treating swine wastewater have been assessed by Wu *et al.* (2016b), Masi
119 *et al.* (2017) and Lin *et al.* (2020) with the main goal to achieve higher OM and nutrients content
120 removal rates in less time and area of land needed (He *et al.*, 2016; Ilyas and Masih, 2017a,b). It
121 has been shown that in aerated horizontal flow (HF) and aerated vertical flow (VF), N removal is
122 more effective than only horizontal flow or vertical flow designs. In fact, removal efficiencies on
123 N increased by applying intermittent aeration with multiple on-off aeration cycles per day (Dotro
124 *et al.*, 2017). In addition, Borin *et al.* (2013) evaluated the performance of different hybrid-
125 constructed wetlands treating swine effluents. Among the hybrid systems presented in their study
126 the system dealing with the highest chemical oxygen demand (COD) and total nitrogen (TN)
127 concentrations reached 4,413 mg COD l⁻¹ and 709 mg TN l⁻¹. Comparing Borin's *et al.* (2013)
128 work with the hybrid (vertical and horizontal subsurface flow) aerated constructed wetland (ACW)
129 under evaluation in this study, this latter would treat six to four times higher concentrations.

130

131 Although the success of intermittent aeration and recirculation strategies have been established,
132 most were carried out at a lab scale (Feng *et al.*, 2020a; Jia *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, a system,
133 which combines NH₃ stripping technology with an ACW at a pilot scale has not been tested before.

134 Considering the facts mentioned above, this study aims to:

- 135 • Evaluate the technological potential of NH₃ stripping with HNO₃ as a washing agent and the
136 quality of AN solution recovered
- 137 • Evaluate the replacement of biological NDN treatment of swine wastewater by NH₃ stripping
138 together with ACW in terms of nutrient removal and treatment cost.

139

140 **2. MATERIALS & METHODS**

141 **2.1 Conventional manure treatment at swine husbandry farm**

142 The current study was conducted at the swine husbandry farm in Gistel-Zevekote, Belgium, with
143 a capacity to raise 11,000 porkers and 5,400 piglets. The conventional manure processing system
144 consists of an AD for biogas production, a decanter centrifuge for physical separation and a
145 biological wastewater treatment plant for the removal of organic and inorganic residues. Manure

146 is first separated into a solid (SF) and a liquid fraction (LF), and the SF is anaerobically treated.
147 The anaerobic digester has the capacity to yearly process about 12,500 t of manure and co-
148 substrates, producing around 1,400 MWh of electricity. The generated digestate is firstly separated
149 by centrifugation into a LF and a SF. The SF is subsequently composted whereas the LF of digestate
150 is mixed with the LF of manure for subsequent biological NDN treatment (about 29,565 t y⁻¹). The
151 effluent from this biological step needs further purification via a CW to meet the Flemish discharge
152 limits.

153

154 **2.2 Alternative manure processing for mineral-N recovery and water purification**

155 In the alternative process (Figure 1), the biological treatment was replaced by a two-step treatment
156 consisting of NH₃ stripping and ACW. The NH₃ stripping is a pilot installation developed by
157 Detricon BV (Belgium) with the capacity to process about one tonne of liquid stream per hour. The
158 NH₃ stripping installation is a cylinder with a height of 8 m and a diameter of 3 m. The packaging
159 material is made of steel and has the form of an open cylinder with a diameter of 10 cm. The stream
160 treated in the NH₃ stripping pilot is a mixture of LF digestate and LF manure, usually in a ratio of
161 1:1. The stripping column is partially filled with packing material and has an air speed of 0.2 - 0.8
162 m s⁻¹. The air enriched with stripped NH₃ is sent to a scrubber column where 60% HNO₃ solution
163 is added as a sorbent to generate AN solution.

164 The N-reduced effluent from the NH₃ stripper is then treated by a two-stage pilot process, a vertical
165 subsurface flow (VSSF) and a horizontal subsurface flow (HSSF) ACW. The ACW is based on a
166 concept called “Forced Bed Aeration (FBA)TM developed by Naturally Wallace Consulting (USA).
167 The hybrid ACW (VSSF-HSSF) was divided into two equal parts which were linked with a
168 pressure-driven tubing system, making the effluent of the first part the influent of the second part.
169 The ACW was sealed from the underground by means of a flexible polypropylene liner, 1 mm
170 thick and filled with 100 m³ of round expanded clay aggregates (Argex®) as substrate. The ACW
171 has a 20 m length, 5 m width, and 1.25 m depth of which 1.10 m are filled with the expanded clay
172 aggregates. This was used because it has a higher specific surface (porous) and it is more economic
173 than gravel in Belgium. The substrate was continuously water-saturated, containing 32 m³ of water
174 in the pore space. It was equipped with perforated tubes at the bottom of the ACW to provide the
175 required airflow through the water column. For this, 41 pipes with a 12 cm separation between
176 each were incorporated into the system. Dimensioning of the ACW was based on 100

177 gBOD/m².day on the VSSF part. Figure 2 shows a scheme of the ACW. Aeration was set for 50%
 178 of the cycle (240 minutes of aeration followed by 240 minutes off). When aeration was reduced
 179 due to clogging of the aeration tubing by iron deposits (seven months after installation), a longer
 180 aeration cycle (240 minutes on and 30 minutes non-aeration) was applied.

181
 182
 183 Figure 1. Process flow of the proposed swine wastewater processing steps by subsequent NH₃ stripping
 184 and aerated constructed wetland: vertical subsurface flow (VSSF) and horizontal subsurface flow (HSSF).
 185 Numbers in black show the five different sampling locations: influent stripper (1), ammonium nitrate
 186 (AN) solution (2), effluent stripper (3), intermediate wetland effluent (4) and wetland effluent (5).

187
 188 Figure 2: Scheme of the ACW. In black, the groundwork is shown indicating the dimensions of the ACW.
 189 At the bottom left the -/- 0,65: represents that the basis of the wetland is 65 cm deep under the rest of the
 190 terrain. The 1.25 m to the right indicates the total depth of the basin. The central pipe (in orange)
 191 represents the distribution pipe of influent coming from the stripper/scrubber. This pipe is connected to the
 192 pump in the pump well. The orange pipe on top of the wetland has holes of 8 mm Ø every 3 meters. There
 193 are 5 holes in total.

194

195 **2.3 Monitoring and sampling overview**

196 The monitoring of the proposed process was performed over three periods:

- 197 • Period 1: from May 9th, 2019, to August 18th, 2019
- 198 • Period 2: from August 18th, 2019, to December 10th, 2019
- 199 • Period 3: from September 10th to December 3rd, 2020.

200 During Periods 1 and 2 samples were collected on a weekly basis, whereas during Period 3 samples
201 were collected once every two weeks. Five different sampling locations, numbered in Figure 1,
202 were considered for monitoring purposes:

- 203 1. influent of the NH₃ stripping unit (IS)
- 204 2. AN solution
- 205 3. effluent of the NH₃ stripping unit (ES), which also corresponds to the influent of the ACW
- 206 4. intermediate effluent of the wetland (IW)
- 207 5. effluent of the wetland (EW).

208
209 The NH₃ stripping installation was operated a few hours a day to ensure enough feed for the ACW.
210 The ES in excess was treated with the conventional biological NDN system in operation at the
211 swine husbandry farm. The NH₃ stripping pilot was monitored over two sampling campaigns
212 (periods 1 and 2), whereas, the ACW was monitored over all three sampling periods. Regarding
213 the ACW, the initial proposed loading rate was 1 m³ day⁻¹. However, due to the clogging of the
214 aeration tubing during preliminary tests, this was lowered on average to 0.571 m³ d⁻¹ during period
215 1 and period 2. Period 1 is considered the acclimatisation phase. Between July 18th and August 16th
216 2019, no data was recorded due to reparations performed to the ACW, during which the ACW was
217 partly cleared and refilled with fresh water coming from the effluent of an adjacent CW that was
218 in operation for 14 years. Once the ACW was filled, ES was fed again during period 2 (0.571 m³
219 d⁻¹). Between period 2 and period 3 the ACW was not fed due to nine months of COVID
220 restrictions, after which the third monitoring campaign was carried out (period 3). In this period,
221 the ACW came back into operation at a reduced loading rate (0.357 m³ d⁻¹) to allow longer retention
222 time, thus higher removal rate.

223

224

225

226 **2.4 Laboratory analyses**

227 After sampling, water samples were immediately transported to the laboratory and stored at 4 °C
228 to be analysed respecting the holding time of each parameter. The executed physicochemical
229 analyses per sample are shown in Table S1 (supplementary material). The values of pH and
230 Electrical Conductivity (EC) were measured directly with a pH probe (Orion Star A211 USA) and
231 a conductivity probe (Orion Star A212 USA). Dry matter (DM) was assessed as the residual weight
232 after 24 h drying at 105 °C. Suspended solids (SS) were measured by filtering a known weight of
233 a sample, drying the filter with the solids, and then weighing the filter to determine the difference
234 between the weight of the clean filter and the filter with solids. Equation 1 shows the formula to
235 calculate SS concentration:

$$236 \text{ SS (mg g}^{-1}\text{)} = (\text{Wfss} - \text{Wf}) / \text{Ws} * 1000 \quad (1)$$

237 where Wfss (g) is the weight of the filter with suspended solids, Wf (g) is the weight of the clean
238 filter, and Ws (g) is the weight of the sample.

239 Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) concentrations were determined through a respirometric
240 method according to the Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater (Eaton
241 *et al.*, 1998). BOD concentrations (mg kg⁻¹) were determined based on the amount of dissolved
242 oxygen consumed by aerobic biological organisms at 20°C for 5 days of incubation. COD content
243 was determined through the spectrophotometric method using NANOCOLOR® test kits
244 (MACHEREY-NAGEL GmbH & Co. KG), range 15–160 mg l⁻¹. TN, ammonium-N (NH₄-N) and
245 nitrate-N (NO₃-N) concentrations were measured by quick test kits (NANOCOLOR, MN985088,
246 MN985005 & MN985064) respectively. Potassium (K), sulphur (S), calcium (Ca), magnesium
247 (Mg) and sodium (Na) were determined using Inductively Coupled Plasma – Optical Emission
248 Spectrophotometry (ICP-OES Varian MPX, USA). IS, ES and IW were analysed after microwave
249 digestion (10 ml 65% HNO₃), whereas AN solution and EW were analysed after wet digestion (2
250 ml of 65% HNO₃ + 1 ml of H₂O₂). Cu and Zn were detected following the same procedure but only
251 on AN solution. Total Organic Carbon (TOC) was calculated as the difference between total carbon
252 (TC) and inorganic carbon (IC), previously determined via a C/N analyser (Skalar B.V., the
253 Netherlands).

254

255

256

257 **2.5 Calculations & statistical analyses**

258 **2.5.1 Material balance**

259 To evaluate the performance of the NH₃ stripping pilot unit, a material balance was carried out per
260 tonne of swine wastewater processed (IS). The mass of ES was calculated based on the difference
261 in DM content between IS and ES. The mass flow of AN solution was calculated assuming that
262 NH₄-N removed in the stripping step was entirely recovered, and thus no NH₃ losses occurred
263 during the adsorption step. The amount of 60% HNO₃ solution was calculated based on the mass
264 of NO₃-N in the AN solution.

265

266 **2.5.2 Calculation of recovery and removal efficiencies**

267 Recovery efficiencies (R_c) of the NH₃ stripping unit stands for the mass of TN, NH₄-N and COD
268 in AN solution as a proportion of the total input from the stripper influent (Eq. 2) (Svarovsky, 1985)

$$269 \quad \% R_c = ((X * C_x) / (Y * C_y)) * 100 \quad (2)$$

270 where X (kg) is the mass of AN solution; C_x (g kg⁻¹ FW) is the concentration of NH₄-N or COD
271 in AN solution; Y (kg) is the mass of IS; C_y (g kg⁻¹ FW) the concentration of TN, NH₄-N or COD
272 in the IS.

273 To determine the percentage of removal efficiencies (R_m) achieved by the ACW design, the
274 difference between the effluent and influent concentrations of the above-mentioned
275 physicochemical parameters was considered (Eq. 3)

$$276 \quad \% R_m = ((C_w - C_z) / C_w) * 100 \quad (3)$$

277 C_z (mg kg⁻¹ FW) the concentration of NH₄-N, NO₃-N, P, SS BOD, or COD in EW; C_w (mg kg⁻¹
278 FW) the concentration of NH₄-N, NO₃-N, P, SS, BOD, or COD in ES.

279

280 **2.5.3 Statistical modelling and parameters estimate**

281 The difference between the ACW effluent and influent concentrations (Diff EW-ES) of the above-
282 mentioned parameters (pH, EC, SS, BOD, COD, TN, NO₃-N, NH₄-N and P) were considered as
283 the response variables. Two models were contrasted to test if the design parameters (air
284 temperature, rainfall, and flow) influence the response variables for the tested parameters. The
285 ordinary least-squares (OLS) linear regression model and the robust linear model (RLM) were
286 selected to check for inference robustness due to the small sample size availability. As an additional
287 note, missing values in measured parameters were interpolated via the spline function.

288
 289 These models check the influence of the design parameters for each of the sampled days and then
 290 predict the difference (Diff EW-ES) for each. Eq. (4) describes the resulting model, as follows

$$291 \text{ Diff EW-ES} = \beta_0 t + \beta_1 t \text{ Air_temp} + \beta_2 t \text{ Rainfall} + \beta_3 t \text{ Flow} + \mu t \quad (4)$$

292 Where Diff EW-ES is the average of the difference between the effluent and influent concentration
 293 of the parameter under study; β the estimated coefficient of the design parameter; t equals time or
 294 sampled day, β_0 the intercept unconditional value of the difference, and μ the stochastic
 295 measurement error.

296 Table 1 shows the minimum and maximum reported percentages of removal efficiencies for hybrid
 297 and VSSF CWs treating similar types of wastewater under similar environmental conditions when
 298 this study was carried out. The presented ranges were used in the OLS and the RLM models to test
 299 if the achieved removal efficiencies by the studied design were between the range of what has been
 300 reported in literature.

301
 302 Table 1. Removal efficiencies of hybrid and VSSF constructed wetlands treating similar types of
 303 wastewater reported in literature.

Parameter	Minimum removal efficiency (%)	Maximum removal efficiency (%)	Reference
EC	76	86	(Vázquez et al., 2013)
SS	40	80	(Klomjek, 2016; Torrens et al., 2020)
BOD	75	94	(Torrens et al., 2020)
COD	52	79	(Borin et al., 2013; Maine et al., 2019)
TN	64	75	(Gonzalez et al., 2009; Borin et al., 2013)
NH ₄	60	87	(Comino et al., 2013; Maine et al., 2019)
NO ₃	53	86	(Borin et al., 2013; Comino et al., 2013)
P	61	87	(Borin et al., 2013; Comino et al., 2013)

304
 305 **2.5 Economic assessment**

306 To address the financial viability of the proposed system in comparison with conventional
 307 biological NDN treatment, an economic assessment of the NH₃ stripping step and the ACW was
 308 carried out. The cost for upstream mechanical separation of manure and digestate via decanter
 309 centrifuge was excluded from the study, as this step is also necessary prior to conventional NDN.
 310 A Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) was performed to evaluate the economic viability of the NH₃
 311 stripping pilot. The capital costs for the pilot amounted to 250,000 € and included housing, tubing

312 and valves, electro-mechanical compounds and heat exchanger, electrical board and PLC,
313 ventilator, external heating, storage for nitric acid (22 m³), storage for AN solution (100 m³) and,
314 sensors (pH, conductivity, temperature, pressure). The investment was amortised following Anon
315 (1998) (Eq 5).

$$316 \quad Q = C * (r (1 + r)^n) / ((1 + r)^n - 1) \quad (5)$$

317 where Q represents the periodic amortisation period, C the total investment, r the interest rate (3%)
318 and n the lifespan of the installation (10 years). It was considered that the pilot requires 0.2 full-
319 time equivalent (FTE) to be operated (Detricon, personal communication). Insurance, maintenance,
320 and personnel cost represented 0.24%, 1.4% and 2.5% of the capital cost. Overall, they amounted
321 to 10,488 € y⁻¹. The pilot has an annual working capacity of 8,000 h, meaning processing about
322 8,000 t y⁻¹ of swine wastewater. During the sampling campaign, the electricity requirement of the
323 installation was recorded onsite for four batches: 11 ± 4 kWhel t⁻¹ processed for the stripping batch
324 and 1.9 ± 0.27 kWhel t⁻¹ to empty the stripped effluent and refill the batch with a fresh mixture of
325 stripper influent. Since the farm is provided with solar panels and generates the electricity
326 necessary for the operation of the pilot plant, the energy costs were not included in the economic
327 evaluation. An estimation of the potential cost was carried out considering 0.10 € kWh⁻¹. For the
328 scrubbing step, the cost of 60% HNO₃ solution and tap water amounted respectively to 200 € t⁻¹
329 and 0.15 € t⁻¹. To evaluate the effect of the increasing energy costs on fertilising commodities
330 prices, a comparison between urea prices over the last five years against the calculated price for
331 AN solution in this study (2019) and in March 2022. The cost of 60% HNO₃ for AN solution
332 production was retrieved at 200 and 795 € per tonne of acid solution used in this study and in 2022,
333 whereas urea prices were obtained from the Index Mundi data warehouse. As previously
334 mentioned, the cost of electricity for the operation of the NH₃ stripping pilot was neglected.
335 As part of the CBA, the potential benefit from the trade of AN solution was calculated considering
336 a price of 650-750 € t⁻¹ N (NUTRIMAN project, 2019).

337
338 Regarding the ACW, the cost assessment was performed for a large-scale system, assuming that
339 all wastewater generated at the swine husbandry farm (29,565 t y⁻¹) would be treated via subsequent
340 NH₃ stripping and ACW. The cost for the initial investment was set at 150 € m⁻², of which 10%
341 was for the aeration infrastructure and 90% for the construction of the wetland. Maintenance costs
342 were estimated at 2,000 € y⁻¹ (Rietland BV, personal communication). The purchase of the

343 agricultural land necessary was defined at 70,000 € ha⁻¹ (Notaris, 2021). Following Eq. (5),
344 investment for the wetland and the aeration were amortised at 10% and 20% respectively. The land
345 purchase was amortised at 20 years with an interest rate set at 3%. Electrical energy consumption
346 was estimated considering that the pilot ACW was implemented with a 0.8 kW blower set to work
347 50% of the time. To study the effect of the ACW feeding rate on the total cost of the proposed
348 process, a single variable sensitivity analysis was included. The range of feeding rates considered
349 was between 0.357 and 1.5 m³ d⁻¹ (36-125 m³ ha⁻¹). For the analysis, it was assumed all other costs
350 were not to vary.

351
352 The cost for the treatment of the (digested) LF of manure with the conventional biological NDN
353 system at the swine husbandry farm was determined as follows. The investment was derived
354 knowing that the daily treatment of 50,000 t ranges between 14 and 24 € t⁻¹ (Santonja *et al.*, 2017)
355 and is amortised following Eq. (5) with an equal interest rate amortisation period. This resulted in
356 an investment cost ranging between 1.6 and 2.8 € t⁻¹. Operational costs included the treatment
357 process (9 € t⁻¹), as well as the disposal of final effluent and sludge (4.4 € t⁻¹) following Derden
358 (2020). Overall total cost was defined at 16 € t⁻¹. It must be considered that treatment costs can
359 increase up to 14 € t⁻¹, depending on the use of chemical additives. Thus, the overall cost can be as
360 high as 21 € t⁻¹.

361

362 **3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION**

363 **3.1 NH₃ stripping unit**

364 **3.1.1 Characterisation of ingoing and outgoing streams**

365 Table 2 summarises the physicochemical composition of the investigated NH₃ stripping streams.
366 The stripping phase increased the pH from 8.0 ± 0.35 to 8.5 ± 0.36. Given the fact that CO₂ is about
367 1,000-fold more volatile than NH₃, an increment in pH is usually ascribed to CO₂ stripping
368 (Crittenden *et al.*, 2012). Removal of NH₄-N resulted in a lower EC, TN, and NH₄-N of ES. Even
369 though the NH₃ stripping system did not influence the SS composition of the treated wastewater,
370 it contributed to the reduction of total COD content. The IS treated was characterised by high COD
371 content, probably due to a poor separation step or a low OM degradation during the AD step. On
372 average, the COD content decreased by 13% from 37 ± 4.9 to 32 ± 8.8 g kg⁻¹ FW after
373 approximately 1 hour of HRT at ambient temperature. Finally, no effect was found on NO₃-N and

374 all other macronutrient content, which stayed stable before and after air stripping. Based on
 375 laboratory scale experiments, Bonmati and Flotats (2003) observed a reduction of COD between
 376 20 and 30% when air stripping was applied to raw and digested swine manure.

377 AN solution (21%) was characterised by high EC ($246 \pm 9.4 \text{ mS cm}^{-1}$) due to the presence of N
 378 ionic compound (NH_4^+ stripped from IS and NO_3^- added via HNO_3) and a neutral pH. The $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$:
 379 TN ratio decreased from 0.66 in IS to 0.58 in ES and reached the highest value of 1 in AN solution
 380 ($81 \pm 14 \text{ g TN kg}^{-1} \text{ FW}$). The presence of COD and other nutrients in the AN solution was
 381 negligible.

382
 383 Table 2. Recorded composition (mean \pm standard deviation) on fresh weight (FW) of influent NH_3 stripper
 384 (IS), effluent NH_3 stripper (ES), and ammonium nitrate (AN) solution in Periods 1 and 2.

	Unit	IS	ES	AN solution
pH		8.0 ± 0.35	8.5 ± 0.36	6.2 ± 0.25
EC	mS cm^{-1}	35 ± 3.5	28 ± 5.8	246 ± 9.4
DM	$\text{g kg}^{-1} \text{ FW}$	35 ± 3.3	34 ± 5.2	210 ± 9.0
SS	$\text{mg g}^{-1} \text{ FW}$	17 ± 3.5	16 ± 7.4	-
COD	$\text{g l}^{-1} \text{ FW}$	37 ± 4.9	32 ± 8.8	0.52 ± 0.19
TN	$\text{g kg}^{-1} \text{ FW}$	5.1 ± 0.75	4.0 ± 1.0	81 ± 14
$\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$	$\text{g kg}^{-1} \text{ FW}$	3.3 ± 0.49	2.2 ± 0.62	39 ± 2.6
$\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$	$\text{g kg}^{-1} \text{ FW}$	0.063 ± 0.012	0.072 ± 0.041	39 ± 4.6
P	$\text{g kg}^{-1} \text{ FW}$	0.33 ± 0.041	0.33 ± 0.080	0.074 ± 0.0093
K	$\text{g kg}^{-1} \text{ FW}$	4.1 ± 0.34	4.2 ± 0.65	1.4 ± 0.15
S	$\text{g kg}^{-1} \text{ FW}$	0.54 ± 0.072	0.58 ± 0.15	0.37 ± 0.061
Ca	$\text{g kg}^{-1} \text{ FW}$	0.73 ± 0.12	0.77 ± 0.22	0.51 ± 0.061
Mg	$\text{g kg}^{-1} \text{ FW}$	0.15 ± 0.044	0.15 ± 0.058	0.080 ± 0.0052
Na	$\text{g kg}^{-1} \text{ FW}$	1.4 ± 0.069	1.5 ± 0.043	0.58 ± 0.085

385
 386 **3.1.2 Material balance and mineral nitrogen recovery**
 387 A thorough material balance of macronutrients was assessed for the NH_3 stripping unit relying on
 388 60% HNO_3 solution as an absorption agent. The treatment of 1 t of swine wastewater resulted in
 389 the production of 27 kg of 21% AN solution, amounting to 1.1 kg of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ recovered per tonne
 390 processed in the NH_3 stripping unit. The recovered $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ makes up 50% of the TN content of the
 391 produced fertilising solution because the added HNO_3 solution (absorption agent) provides the
 392 remaining 50% in the form of $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$. The use of HNO_3 instead of H_2SO_4 results in higher N
 393 concentrations in the recovered NH_4 salts which translates into important agronomic advantages.
 394 Overall, 21% of TN (32% of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$) contained in IS was recovered in the form of AN solution

395 (81 ± 14 g kg⁻¹ of TN). Since only mineral-N is removed during the process, the amount of organic-
 396 N was not affected (Figure 3). This NH₄-N removal efficiency was achieved neither by heating the
 397 ingoing mixture of LF manure and LF digestate nor by adding any base to increment pH conditions.
 398 Therefore, these results represent the removal efficiencies with the lowest energy input and
 399 chemical use. It can be expected that the removal efficiencies can be significantly increased at
 400 higher temperatures and pH conditions (Zarebska *et al.*, 2015).

401 As a result of the material balance performed in this study, the consumption of 60% HNO₃
 402 amounted to 7.7 kg kg⁻¹ N recovered. Similarly, Brienza *et al.* (2021) reported the use of 7.3 kg of
 403 50% H₂SO₄ and 8.4 kg of CaSO₄.2H₂O (75% DM) to recuperate 1 kg of N in different full-scale
 404 NH₃ stripping units.

405

406
 407 Figure 3. Material balance of organic nitrogen (Org-N), nitrate nitrogen (NO₃-N) and ammonium nitrogen
 408 (NH₄-N) for 1 tonne of animal wastewater processed.

409

410 Regarding all other macronutrients (P, K, S, Ca, Mg and Na), their contents were similar before
 411 and after NH₃ stripping and thus their mass flow resulted in equilibrium (Table 3). Differently from
 412 vacuum NH₃ stripping (Brienza *et al.*, 2021), the ambient conditions operated by DetriCon did not
 413 result in water evaporation and up-concentration of the IS components. On the other hand, although
 414 air stripping contributed to removing around 13% of the COD from IS, less than 1% was found in

415 the recovered AN solution. Bonmati and Flotats (2003) recorded COD losses higher than 5% when
 416 H₂SO₄ was used to recover stripped N. These results suggest that neither HNO₃ nor H₂SO₄
 417 successfully fixed volatile organics, and therefore further air treatment is required to prevent
 418 detrimental effects on the environment. Yet, further research should aim to investigate possible
 419 COD degradation pathways during NH₃ stripping.

420

421 Table 3. Material balance of the NH₃ stripping unit in the Periods 1 and 2.

Parameter	IS (kg)	ES (kg)	60% HNO ₃ solution (kg)	AN solution (kg)
Mass	1000	998	8.1	27
Water	965	965	3.2	22
DM	35	33	4.8	5.7
COD	37	32	-	0.014
P	0.33	0.33	-	0.0020
K	4.1	4.2	-	0.038
S	0.54	0.58	-	0.010
Ca	0.73	0.77	-	0.014
Mg	0.15	0.15	-	0.0022
Na	1.4	1.5	-	0.016

422

423 The implementation of NH₃ stripping technology to the AD of animal manure has been investigated
 424 at both pilot and full-scale. On a pilot scale, Pintucci *et al.* (2017) recovered between 35 and 39%
 425 of NH₄-N, depending on the air recirculation rate. Bolzonella *et al.* (2018) monitored a system
 426 where the LF of digested swine and cow manure entered in an NH₃ stripping unit and 22% of TN
 427 was recovered from the stripper influent, resulting in ammonium sulphate solution (26 g kg⁻¹ TN).
 428 In 2018, Baldi and co-authors conducted a series of trials at different operative conditions and
 429 recorded NH₄-N removals ranging between 22% and 66%. Brienza *et al.* (2021) monitored a full-
 430 scale vacuum side stream NH₃ stripping installation relying on flue gas desulphurisation with
 431 CaSO₄.2H₂O as an absorption agent. The authors recorded 31% of TN (57% of NH₄-N) recovery
 432 from raw digestate in the form of ammonium sulphate solution (46 ± 3.6 g kg⁻¹ of TN). Differently
 433 from the two previous cases, Ledda *et al.* (2013) described a digestate processing cascade where
 434 LF digestate was processed in a membrane filtration system and subsequently its retentate flowed
 435 in an NH₃ stripping system. The N recovery rates differed when digestate originated from cattle or
 436 swine manure. The former resulted in 74% TN recovery (78% NH₄-N), while the latter led to 71%
 437 recovery of TN (73% of NH₄-N) from the ingoing reverse osmosis retentate. In both cases, H₂SO₄
 438 was used as an absorption agent, generating ammonium sulphate solution (51-61 g kg⁻¹ TN). The

439 efficiency of the NH₃ stripping pilot in our study achieved 21% of TN (32% of NH₄-N), which is
440 overall equal to or lower than the literature results. However, this was achieved at ambient pH and
441 temperature. Also, the high COD content could have jeopardised the rate of NH₃ volatilisation, due
442 to the binding of NH₄⁺ by OM (Kinniburgh *et al.*, 1996; Hafner *et al.*, 2006), limiting the efficiency
443 of the stripping process.

444

445 ***3.1.3 Agricultural value of ammonium nitrate solution***

446 The biobased AN solution generated by Detricon pilot plant fulfils all quality criteria needed to be
447 recognised as both RENURE product (Huygens *et al.*, 2020) and as straight liquid inorganic
448 macronutrient fertiliser (PFC 1(C)(I)(b)(i)), according to the European FPR (EU) 1009/2019 (Table
449 4). TN content is 1.6 times of the minimum content required and TOC is 40-fold lower than the
450 maximum allowed by the FPR. In the proposal drafted after the public consultation, the
451 amendments add a new component material category (CMC 15, “Recovered high purity
452 materials”), which would include NH₄ salts if these are 95% pure, (with no more than 0.5% of OC)
453 on DM basis. If so, AN solution from Detricon may be used as mineral fertiliser under the same
454 prescriptions of synthetic fertilisers.

455 Regarding RENURE criteria, AN solution complies with both the maximal TOC:TN and the
456 mineral N:TN ratio, despite it being sufficient to meet just one of the two. Regarding Cu and Zn,
457 their content in the fertilising solution is largely below RENURE and FPR limits. According to its
458 compositional characteristics, the AN solution generated by Detricon represents an interesting
459 option to replace synthetic N fertilisers and to recycle mineral-N of manure origin. Currently,
460 ammonium sulphate generated from NH₃ stripping plants and retentate from membrane filtration
461 installations have demonstrated to meet RENURE quality standards proposed by the JRC (Brienza
462 *et al.*, 2021; van Puffelen *et al.*, 2022).

463

464 Table 4. Characteristics requirements for the denomination of different fertilisers defined by the Fertilising
465 Product Regulation (EU) 1009/2019 and Joint Research Centre (JRC) RENURE products (Huygens *et al.*,
466 2020), in comparison with biobased ammonium nitrate generated by Detricon (FW: fresh weight; DW: dry
467 weight).

468

Fertiliser type	TN (g kg ⁻¹ FW)	TOC (g kg ⁻¹ FW)	TOC:TN	mineral- N _i :TN (%)	Cu (mg kg ⁻¹ DW)	Zn (mg kg ⁻¹ DW)
PFC 1(C)(I)(b)(i) (Fertilising Product Regulation)	≥ 50	≤ 10			≤ 600	≤ 1500
RENURE product (JRC)			≤ 3*	≥ 90*	≤ 300	≤ 800
Ammonium nitrate (Detricon)	81 ± 14	0.24 ± 0.042	0.0029	100	62 ± 16	118 ± 42

*For RENURE products either the threshold for TOC:TN ratio or NH₄-N:TN ratio should be met.

469
470

471 To evaluate the potential of AN solution as a replacement for broadcast synthetic fertilisers, pot
472 and field trials were set up by Sigurnjak *et al* (2019). The authors also investigated the
473 environmental impact of AN application in terms of postharvest NO₃⁻ residue. The agronomic
474 performance of biobased AN generated by Detricon was assessed in comparison with calcium
475 ammonium nitrate (CAN) of synthetic origin. Pot experiments were performed on lettuce where
476 the application of AN solution resulted in slightly higher crop yields and consequently N uptake
477 compared to the commercial mineral fertilisation regime. AN performance on a field scale was
478 assessed in maize cultivation, in comparison with a reference treatment of animal manure, and
479 CAN: crop yields and N uptake were similar in both cases. Moreover, the postharvest NO₃-N
480 residue after AN fertilisation was below the amount allowed by the Flemish legislation (90 kg NO₃-
481 N ha⁻¹ in 0-90 cm soil) and comparable to the reference treatments (Sigurnjak *et al.*, 2019). The
482 neutral pH of this biobased fertiliser reduces the risk of machinery erosion, yet, its application can
483 lead to NH₃ volatilisation and loss in the atmosphere. As such, correct agronomical practices (e.g.
484 injection into soil or fast incorporation after surface application) are required to alleviate adverse
485 environmental effects (Huygens *et al.*, 2020).

486

487 **3.2 Aerated constructed wetland**

488 **3.2.1 Removal efficiencies**

489 The percentages of removal efficiencies (R_m) achieved by the ACW design were calculated and
490 are presented in Table 5. Considering that Period 1 represented the acclimatisation stage, average
491 removal efficiencies were determined based on data collected during Periods 2 and 3. The
492 comparison of R_m achieved between the ACW compartments proves the efficiency of the designed
493 system. It is seen that R_m increase from the first to the second compartment and from the beginning

494 to the end of the ACW system. It is important to note that readily biodegradable COD is promptly
 495 removed in the first compartment, different from the other parameters, which removal efficiency
 496 increases as wastewater passes through the system. Overall, the Rm for all parameters of the whole
 497 ACW ranged between 80% and 97%, except for NO₃-N (Table 5).

498
 499 Table 5. Average concentrations of influent wetland (effluent stripper, ES), intermediate aerated
 500 constructed wetland effluent (IW), effluent aerated constructed wetland (EW) and removal efficiencies
 501 achieved by the aerated constructed wetland (ACW) by the end of Period 3, compared to effluent
 502 composition of typical biological nitrification-denitrification (NDN) treatment plant reported by Lemmens
 503 *et al.*, (2007) (FW: fresh weight).

Parameter	ES (mg kg ⁻¹ FW)	IW (mg kg ⁻¹ FW)	EW (mg kg ⁻¹ FW)	Rm in the first part of the ACW (%)	Rm in the second part of the ACW (%)	Rm of the whole ACW (%)	Effluent NDN (mg kg ⁻¹ FW)
SS	14	5.0	0.55	62%	87%	96%	
BOD	2,370	554	80	76%	86%	96%	10 - 100
COD	26,875	13,843	2,787	90%	76%	90%	1,000 - 5,000
TN	2,861	2,186	509	27%	74%	80%	500
NH ₄ -N	1,788	1,346	119	18%	93%	95%	0 - 20
NO ₃ -N	67	228	224	-204%	-181%	-632%	250 - 300
P	344	131	8.7	57%	91%	97%	130 - 220

504
 505 Figures 4 (a), 5 (a) and 6 (a) show higher variability in recorded data given the slow recovery of
 506 the ACW system after the performed repairs between periods 1 and 2. Conversely, Figures 4 (b),
 507 5 (b) and 6 (b) show major stability in the system after nine months of continuous work under lower
 508 flow, which results in a longer retention time and higher removal rates.

509
 510 The NO₃-N concentrations increased over time due to limited denitrification combined with
 511 effective nitrification of the NH₄-N by the aerated system. OC and NO₃-N concentrations, wetland
 512 vegetation, pH, water depth and temperature are parameters that have been assessed to determine
 513 their influence on denitrification rates. Among these, the available carbon, NO₃-N concentration,
 514 and water depth were the most influential factors (Hunt *et al.*, 2003; Songliu *et al.*, 2009). In this
 515 study, available carbon and high NO₃-N concentration could partially explain the limited
 516 denitrification. Readily available carbon sources could be scarce, due to the lack of plant litter as
 517 no plants grew in the system, this could happen due to high TN concentrations that resulted in no
 518 plants' survival or mainly due to the type of wastewater treated by the system.

519 Constructed wetlands treating the liquid fraction of piggery manure have to deal with fractions of
 520 recalcitrant or non-biodegradable OM which shows high COD concentrations and relatively low
 521 BOD concentrations (Donoso *et al.*, 2019). Thus, a relatively high COD could imply that there was
 522 not sufficient biodegradable OC thus incomplete denitrification prevailed as was observed by
 523 Donoso *et al.* (2019) for this type of effluent to be treated. Additionally, Fan *et al.* (2013), Wu *et al.*
 524 *et al.* (2016a), Hou *et al.* (2017) and Donoso *et al.* (2019) concluded that intermittent aeration could
 525 favour TN removal when there are longer non-aerated periods than aerated ones. In this study,
 526 however, non-aerated periods were reduced to minimise the continuous clogging of aeration pipes
 527 with large particles contained in the ES. Another reason that can explain the limited nitrate removal,
 528 lies in the prompt availability of ammonia-oxidizing bacteria to promote the oxidation of NH_4^+ to
 529 nitrite (NO_2^-), and then to NO_3^- at the beginning of Period 2. However, during mid Period 2 and 3,
 530 Figure 4 shows that aeration could have altered the microbial community properties and
 531 composition. Shirdashtzadeh *et al.* (2022) after studying factors that influence microbial
 532 communities and their behaviour on N removal, reported that among the regulating factors,
 533 dissolved oxygen and N concentration significantly influence microbial diversity and composition.
 534

535
 536
 537 Figure 4. $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}:\text{TN}$ ratio of removal concentrations achieved in the ACW during the second period in (a)
 538 and third period in (b) considering the sampling date.

539
 540 Contrary to the accumulated $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ effect, the ideal conditions encountered in the system for
 541 nitrification, (such as oxic conditions and pH values above 6.8) resulted in high $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ removal
 542 rates (Figure 5).

543

544
 545
 546 Figure 5. $\text{NH}_4\text{-N:TN}$ ratio of removal concentrations achieved in the ACW during the second period in a)
 547 and third period in b) considering the sampling date.

548
 549 According to literature (Samudro and Mangkoedihardjo, 2010; Abdalla and Hammam, 2014;
 550 Lakhlifi *et al.*, 2017), BOD:COD ratios below 0.3 indicate non-biodegradable wastewater. Thus,
 551 the smallest recorded ratios were the ones of the wetland effluent where the COD values represent
 552 recalcitrant OM. The low BOD:COD ratios in ES (<0.3, Figure 6) but high COD removal rates
 553 (90%, Table 5) indicate that this ACW can treat wastewater containing not easily biodegradable
 554 OM as the residue after AD and stripping.

555

556
 557
 558 Figure 6. BOD:COD ratio of removal concentrations achieved in the ACW during the second period in a)
 559 and the third period in b) considering the sampling date.

560

561 Furthermore, the P removal was enhanced due to artificial aeration given the redox, managing with
 562 aeration strategies that facilitate processes, such as chemical precipitation and/or binding to iron in

563 the substrate. Ilyas and Masih (2018) reported that major processes participating in P removal are
564 soil sorption and chemical precipitation, whereas plant and microbial uptake play a moderate to
565 low role.

566 On the other hand, 96% of SS removal is similar to the 97% achieved by Masi *et al.* (2017) in a
567 system that coupled an anaerobic sludge blanket with an intensified constructed wetland (aerated
568 CWs) to treat swine wastewater at pilot scale. At the intensified aerated vertical subsurface flow
569 CWs, the maximum removal was achieved. The processes through which SS are removed are the
570 absorption and retention of inert SS inside the substrate, the biodegradation of OM that converts
571 into biosolids and the transformation of biomass residues into inert solids through microbial
572 endogenous respiration (Hua *et al.*, 2013).

573 Comparing the effluent composition achieved by the NH₃ stripping and ACW system, with the
574 effluent quality of a typical biological NDN treatment plant (Table 5), the EW concentrations are
575 similar for BOD, COD and TN. The P content in EW (224 mg kg⁻¹) is 15-25 times lower compared
576 to the average NDN effluent. Yet, further research would be necessary to establish if this is a long-
577 term removal process or if the ACW will reach a quick saturation. On the other hand, the achieved
578 effluent NH₄-N concentrations of 119 mg.kg⁻¹ at the EW compared to the 0–20 mg.kg⁻¹ of the
579 effluent NDN indicates that the proposed system did not reach as high removal concentrations of
580 NH₄-N as the NDN and, in consequence, of NO₃-N. Thus, the tested system combining NH₃ stripping
581 and ACW could replace a conventional biological treatment, provided that higher NH₄-N and NO₃-
582 N removal rates are achieved. Increased NH₄-N removals could be achieved for instance by
583 increasing the temperature during the NH₃ stripping step, with the excess heat generated by the AD
584 plant. CW can also contribute to further polishing of the effluent prior to discharge on surface
585 water.

586

587 **3.2.2 Statistical modelling and parameter estimates**

588 This section presents an interpretation of the results for the two contrasted models, the OLS and
589 RLM. Statistical analyses were conducted for all the response variables of the parameters under
590 study. Appendix A. Supplementary material shows the results and graphs for the run models
591 (Nyieku *et al.*, 2021). For illustration purposes and to explain how results were interpreted Table 6
592 and Figure 7 show OLS results, while Table 7 and Figure 8 present RLM results. The median value
593 (-0.0017) less or close to zero indicates the model can be interpreted, and that there is no indication

594 of specification problems. The statistically significant intercept indicates that BOD concentrations’
 595 removal is on average greater than 0. Regarding the control parameters among air temperature,
 596 rainfall, and flow, only flow affects statistically the BOD removal according to OLS model. The
 597 adjusted R-squared, indicates that for the BOD the design parameters together explain 13% of its
 598 variability. Predictions in blue, in Figure 7 indicate that in this study the average removal of the
 599 BOD is higher than the removal reported in the literature (75-94%; Table 1), for CWs treating the
 600 same type of wastewater working at similar environmental conditions.

601

602 Table 6. Ordinary least-squares model output for biological oxygen demand & contrast

lm (formula = BODdiff.interp ~ Air_temp + Rainfall + Flow, data = wetland.data)					
Residuals:					
	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-0.11689	-0.01248	-0.0017	0.02278	0.06412
Coefficients:					
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr (> t)	
(Intercept)	1.01	3.07e-02	32.99	<2e-16***	
Air_temp	4.05e-05	1.84e-03	0.02	0.98	
Rainfall	-7.42e-03	5.26e-03	-1.41	0.18	
Flow	-6.14e-05	2.86e-05	-2.15	0.05*	
Significant codes	0	0.001 ***	0.01 **	0.05 *	0.1
Multiple R-squared:	0.2567		Adjusted R-squared: 0.1255		
F-statistic:	1.957 on 3 and 17 DF		p-value: 0.1589		

603

604 Figure 7. Ordinary least-squares model graph for biological oxygen demand indicating the difference
 605 between the ACW effluent and influent concentrations. The blue line shows the predictions. Confidence
 606 intervals in red are plotted vs. timestamps. Time stamps should be understood as the sampling times
 607 following the reported dates. The dotted lines in black show the maximum and minimum values reported
 608 in literature for BOD removal by VSSF or hybrid CWs treating swine wastewater. Removal pct represents
 609 removal percentage.

610
 611 Following with the statistical analysis, the RLM model was estimated, due to the small sample size.
 612 Both models need to be contrasted to express results with more certainty. Differences between both
 613 models could imply, conclusions cannot be estimated or not with full certainty. For example, the
 614 RLM model results show that the effect of flow in the mean difference of BOD is not sufficiently
 615 high to be explained by this model, or the sample size is too small to conclude with certitude. This
 616 is seen by the absolute t value (-2.008), which is lower than the critical value for a two-tailed t-
 617 distribution, 2.11, with 17 degrees of freedom. Nonetheless, Figure 8 shows that the graph of this
 618 model is very similar to the prior behaviour, and the t value of the intercept in Table 7 proves that
 619 the mean difference of the dependent variable is not zero.

620

621 Table 7. Regression linear model output for biological oxygen demand & contrast

rlm (formula = BODdiff.interp ~ Air_temp + Rainfall + Flow, data = wetland.data)					
Residuals:					
	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-0.1336	-0.0176	-0.0037	0.0227	0.0487
Coefficients:					
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value		
(Intercept)	0.997	0.024	41.66		
Air_temp	0.0005	0.0014	0.345		
Rainfall	-0.005	0.0041	-1.225		
Flow	0.000	0.000	-2.008		
Residual standard error: 0.02973 on 17 degrees of freedom					

BOD EW-ES: RLM

622

623 Figure 8. Regression linear model graph for biological oxygen demand indicating the difference between
624 the ACW effluent and influent concentrations. The blue line shows the predictions. Confidence intervals
625 in red are plotted vs. timestamps. Time stamps should be understood as the sampling times following the
626 reported dates. Dotted lines in black show the maximum and minimum values reported in literature for
627 BOD removal by VSSF or hybrid CWs treating swine wastewater. Removal pct represents, removal
628 percentage.

629

630 Results of all the other studied parameters for both models indicate that the mean difference
631 between the ACW effluent and influent concentrations of EC (Tables S4 and S5), SS (Tables S6
632 and S7), and TN (Tables S10 and S11) are influenced by the flow. For the specific case of P, only
633 the RLM model indicates that its mean difference is also influenced by flow (Table S17). The
634 adjusted R-squared indicates that for each of them, the design parameters together explain 77% of
635 EC, 36% of SS, and 45% of TN of the observed variability. Differently, the mean difference
636 between the ACW effluent and influent concentrations of pH and COD are influenced by
637 temperature. For these parameters, the adjusted R-squared indicates that this design parameter
638 explains 28% of the observed variability of pH, and 15% of COD. For the case of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, none of
639 the studied design parameters showed influence.

640

641 In conclusion, it can be presumed that for all cases there are other parameters that can be considered
642 in the model to explain better the variability and decrease of the studied physicochemical

643 concentrations. Otherwise, a larger sample size could define better the results of the tested models.
644 It is important to mention that reported studies, among few (Gonzalez *et al.*, 2009; Borin *et al.*,
645 2013; Comino *et al.*, 2013; Vázquez *et al.*, 2013; Klomjek, 2016; Maine *et al.*, 2019; Torrens *et*
646 *al.*, 2020) do not consider meteorological influence, as air temperature, rainfall, or design
647 parameters as flow, to calculate or report their results.

648 Looking at the OLS and RLM graphs in Appendix A, Figures S3-S14 for EC, SS, COD, TN, NH₄-
649 N and P indicate that in general, the average removal is higher than that reported in literature (Table
650 1). This was achieved thanks to the intermittent aeration in the wetland which helped to decompose
651 OM, and in principle triggered TN removal. Microorganisms will break down carbon sources
652 (BOD, COD) and use oxygen for that. When the aeration is off, they have to use the dissolved
653 oxygen in the wastewater left from the aeration phase, which could be insufficient. This will lead
654 to anoxic and possibly anaerobic conditions needed for denitrification and NO₃⁻ removal (Feng *et*
655 *al.*, 2020b; Parde *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, for this study, further research and development are
656 needed, regarding engineering design and automation in the constructed wetland, mainly aeration
657 rates.

658

659 **3.3 Process economics**

660 **3.3.1 Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) of the NH₃ stripping installation**

661 The electricity needed for the pilot installation amounted to 13 kWh t⁻¹ of IS processed (12 kWh
662 kg⁻¹ N recovered), whereas no thermal energy was required since the process was carried out at
663 ambient conditions. Assuming the same energy consumption for a full-scale system, the amount of
664 electrical energy necessary to process all wastewater generated by the pig farm (29,565 t y⁻¹) would
665 represent about 27% of the total electricity generated at the AD plant (about 1,400 MWh).

666 Our results corroborate the findings of previous work in this field. Vaneekhaute *et al.* (2017)
667 revealed electrical consumptions between 1.5 and 12 kWh m³; requirements in the range of 0.8-28
668 kWh kg⁻¹ N recovered were identified by Tampio *et al.* (2016).

669

670 The results of the CBA analysis are summarised in Table 8. The cost of processing 1 t of mixed
671 LF manure and LF digestate and to generate 27 kg of 21% AN solution amounted to 6.6 € t⁻¹
672 processed, of which more than 50% consists of the initial amortised investment. This is in line with
673 literature values (2.0-8.1 € m³) indicated by Vaneekhaute *et al.* (2017); nevertheless, it is

674 reasonable to think that both investment and operational costs can be reduced when scaling up the
675 installation to full-scale. Moreover, the valorisation of excess heat from CHP engines may increase
676 the profitability of NH₃ stripping at full-scale thanks to advantageous industrial incentives. It must
677 be pointed out, that energy costs were not included since the farm generates all electricity necessary
678 for the operation of the pilot by means of solar panels. In case electricity was purchased, the overall
679 cost would increase by roughly 20%, to 7.9 € t⁻¹ processed. The potential benefit from the trade of
680 biobased AN solution was calculated at 1.4-1.7 € t⁻¹ processed, corresponding on average to 57 €
681 t⁻¹ AN solution produced (8.1% N), in accordance with the market value of N (650-750 € t⁻¹ N,
682 NITROMAN project). The calculated market value for AN solution generated by Detricon (about
683 57 € t⁻¹) is in line with prices estimated for ammonium sulphate solutions from NH₃ stripping
684 installations. Market values ranging from 21 to 35 € t⁻¹ (4.6-8% N) were reported by Lauren *et al.*
685 (2013), Bolzonella *et al.* (2018) and Brienza *et al.* (2021), respectively in Spain, Italy and Germany.
686 The variation of NH₄ salts value can be ascribed to the specificity of each regional market;
687 nonetheless, the higher value AN solution is justified by the higher N content, almost double, in
688 comparison to ammonium sulphate solutions with similar DM content.

689

690 Table 8. Cost Benefit Analysis of ammonium nitrate solution production via NH₃ stripping.

	Cost (€ t ⁻¹ processed)	Benefit (€ t ⁻¹ processed)
Amortised capital cost	3.7	
Electrical energy	0	
60% HNO ₃ solution	1.6	
Insurance, maintenance, labour	1.3	
Ammonium nitrate value		1.5
Total	6.6	1.5

691

692 The cost of AN solution (8.1% N) amounting to 242 € t⁻¹, translates into a cost of 3.0 € kg⁻¹ N.
693 According to IndexMundi, in the same years of our study (2019 and 2020), the price of broadcast
694 synthetic N fertiliser (urea 46% N) was on average 0.46 € kg⁻¹ N (Figure S15). However, the
695 increased energy prices over the last year and a half contributed to the increase in the price of urea
696 by four times, up to 1.8 € kg⁻¹ N. Similarly to urea's cost, also the price for 60% HNO₃
697 quadruplicated from 200 in 2019 to 795 € t⁻¹ in March 2022. Nevertheless, as AN solution produced
698 by NH₃ stripping relies on the renewable electricity generated onsite, the overall production cost

699 calculated in March 2022 increased to 5.2 € kg⁻¹ N, only by 1.7 times, against an increment of 3.9-
700 fold of urea. Although the purchase of synthetic urea is still economically more favourable
701 compared to the cost of producing biobased AN solution, it is worth of notice that in 2019-2020
702 the cost per kg N in AN solution was 6.6 times higher than urea, whereas, in March 2022, it was
703 2.9.

704

705 **3.3.2. Overall cost of the proposed system: NH₃ stripping + ACW**

706 During the last monitoring period, the ACW was fed with 36 m³ ha⁻¹ d⁻¹. With such loading rate, a
707 surface area of 2.3 ha (226 times larger than the actual ACW pilot), would be necessary to replace
708 the biological NDN system of the pig farm. This translates into high investment costs, about 8.7 €
709 t⁻¹ of processed and operational costs of around 3.8 € t⁻¹. The overall cost of the proposed process,
710 consisting of NH₃ stripping (5.1 € t⁻¹) and ACW (12 € t⁻¹) resulted to be slightly more expensive
711 than the conventional biological NDN system (16 € t⁻¹).

712 To investigate the effect of increasing loading rates on the overall process cost, a sensitivity
713 analysis was carried out. Results indicated that the process becomes competitive with NDN only
714 for loading rates higher than 40 m³ ha⁻¹ d⁻¹, which is 12% more of the amount fed during the last
715 period of the monitoring (Figure 9). At the envisaged loading rate in the initial experimental design
716 (1 m³ d⁻¹, corresponding to 100 m³ ha⁻¹), the proposed process would cost 10 € t⁻¹, against 16 € t⁻¹
717 of the current NDN system, thus cheaper than conventional treatment. Yet, to achieve such high
718 treatment capacity, it is of utmost importance to implement baffles in the system and control
719 clogging of pipes by improving solids removal from the treated wastewater.

720

721
 722 Figure 9. Effect of aerated constructed wetland (ACW) increasing loading rate on the overall cost of the
 723 proposed process (NH₃ stripping and ACW), in comparison with conventional biological nitrification-
 724 denitrification (NDN) treatment.

725
 726 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

727 Considering the system design, overall efficiency and estimated costs, this study suggests two
 728 design options for alternative swine wastewater treatment. First, the effluent of NH₃ stripping plus
 729 ACW is brought to land in the right season, yet it must be buffered in winter. Alternatively, the
 730 effluent of the proposed process must be followed by hybrid CW so that the effluent could meet
 731 discharge standards limits for surface water. Despite not being yet economically competitive with
 732 conventional NDN systems, the proposed process has the potential to produce a biobased mineral
 733 fertiliser, AN solution, that meets both FPR and RENURE criteria.

734 In this study design, parameters such as rainfall, air temperature and flow, were considered in two
 735 models, the OLS, and the RLM. The reasoning behind this was to capture their possible incidence
 736 in each of the studied parameters (pH, EC, SS, COD, BOD, TN, NO₃, NH₄ and P) and compare it
 737 with removal ranges reported in the literature. Most of the removal efficiencies of the studied
 738 parameters (EC, SS, TN, partially P and BOD) were influenced by the flow. This proves that it was
 739 suitable to test different flow rates in each sampling period, as these influenced the most to the
 740 mean concentrations decrease. The overall analysis shows that at lower flow, higher removal

741 efficiencies were achieved. The exception was for NO₃-N concentration whose decrease was
742 limited by insufficient denitrification. Thus, the NH₃ stripping step could be optimised to remove
743 more NH₄-N, improving the COD:N ratio in the influent to the ACW.

744 NH₃ stripping plus ACW has the potential to replace the conventional biological NDN system and
745 improve N circularity in livestock-dominated food chains. However, further investigation should
746 validate potential environmental benefits through comprehensive LCA analysis, especially to
747 address concerns regarding intensive land use, and optimise process parameter settings to improve
748 economic viability and environmental impact of these technologies combination.

749

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756

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- 970

971 **APPENDIX A. Supplementary data**

972

973 Table S1. Overview of monitoring periods (Period 1-2-3) and physico-chemical characterisation for each
 974 sampling point: influent stripper (IS), ammonium nitrate (AN) solution, effluent stripper (ES),
 975 intermediate wetland effluent (IW) and wetland effluent (EW).

	IS	AN solution	ES	IW	EW
pH	Period 1-2	Period 1-2	Period 1-2-3	Period 2-3	Period 1-2-3
EC	Period 1-2	Period 1-2	Period 1-2-3	Period 2-3	Period 1-2-3
DM	Period 1-2	Period 1-2	Period 1-2-3	Period 2-3	
SS	Period 1-2	Period 1-2	Period 1-2-3	Period 2-3	Period 1-2-3
COD	Period 1-2	Period 1-2	Period 1-2-3	Period 2-3	Period 1-2-3
BOD			Period 1-2-3	Period 2-3	Period 1-2-3
TN	Period 1-2	Period 1-2	Period 1-2-3	Period 2-3	Period 1-2-3
NH ₄ -N	Period 1-2	Period 1-2	Period 1-2-3	Period 2-3	Period 1-2-3
NO ₃ -N	Period 1-2	Period 1-2	Period 1-2-3	Period 2-3	Period 1-2-3
P	Period 1-2	Period 1-2	Period 1-2-3	Period 2-3	Period 1-2-3
K	Period 1-2	Period 1-2	Period 1-2-3		
S	Period 1-2	Period 1-2	Period 1-2-3		
Ca	Period 1-2	Period 1-2	Period 1-2-3		
Mg	Period 1-2	Period 1-2	Period 1-2-3		
Na	Period 1-2	Period 1-2	Period 1-2-3		
TOC		Period 1-2			
Cu		Period 1-2			
Zn		Period 1-2			

976

977 Table S2: Ordinary least-squares model output pH & contrast

lm (formula = pHdiff.interp ~ Air_temp + Rainfall + Flow, data = wetland.data)					
Residuals:					
	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-0.048920	-0.019464	-0.005367	0.016245	0.067451
Coefficients:					
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr (> t)	
(Intercept)	1.10e-01	2.31e-02	4.78	0.00018***	
Air_temp	-4.39e-03	1.39e-03	-3.18	0.0055**	
Rainfall	3.44e-03	3.97e-03	0.87	0.40	
Flow	1.44e-05	2.16e-05	0.67	0.51*	
Signif. codes	0 ***	0.001 **	0.01 *	0.05	0.1
Multiple R-squared:	0.3842		Adjusted R-squared: 0.2756		
F-statistic:	3.536 on 3 and 17 DF		p-value: 0.03723		

pH EW-ES: OLS

978
 979 Figure S1: Ordinary least-squares model graph for pH indicating the modelled difference between the
 980 ACW effluent and influent concentrations
 981
 982 Table S3: Regression linear model output for pH & contrast

rlm (formula = pHdiff.interp ~ Air_temp + Rainfall + Flow, data = wetland.data)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-0.04715	-0.01561	-0.005262	0.01655	0.06916

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value
(Intercept)	0.106	0.0205	5.174
Air_temp	-0.0046	0.0012	-3.722
Rainfall	0.0031	0.0035	0.884
Flow	0.000	0.000	1.05

Residual standard error: 0.02454 on 17 degrees of freedom

pH EW-ES: RLM

983

984 Figure S2: Robust linear model graph for pH indicating the modelled difference between the ACW
 985 effluent and influent concentrations

986

987 Table S4: Ordinary least-squares model output for electrical conductivity & contrast

lm (formula = ECdiff.interp ~ Air_temp + Rainfall + Flow, data = wetland.data)					
Residuals:					
	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-0.15213	-0.07236	-0.01043	0.09291	0.22965
Coefficients:					
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr (> t)	
(Intercept)	5.10e-01	8.34e-02	6.12	1.14e-05***	
Air_temp	1.33e-02	4.99e-03	2.67	0.016 *	
Rainfall	2.03e-02	1.43e-02	1.42	0.17	
Flow	-5.76e-04	7.77e-05	-7.42	1.01e-06 ***	
Signif. codes	0 ***	0.001 **	0.01 *	0.05	0.1
Multiple R-squared: 0.8028			Adjusted R-squared: 0.768		
F-statistic: 23.07 on 3 and 17 DF			p-value: 3.158e-06		

EC EW-ES: OLS

988
 989 Figure S3: Ordinary least-squares model graph for electrical conductivity indicating the modelled
 990 difference between the ACW effluent and influent concentrations

991
 992 Table S5: Robust linear model output for EC & contrast

rlm (formula = pHdiff.interp ~ Air_temp + Rainfall + Flow, data = wetland.data)					
Residuals:					
	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-0.149548	-0.071860	-0.009106	0.095229	0.234199
Coefficients:					
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value		
(Intercept)	0.5056	0.0885	5.7129		
Air_temp	0.0131	0.0053	2.4720		
Rainfall	0.0202	0.0152	1.3312		
Flow	-0.0006	0.0001	-6.9215		
Residual standard error: 0.1315 on 17 degrees of freedom					

EC EW-ES: RLM

993
 994 Figure S4: Robust linear model graph for electrical conductivity indicating the modelled difference
 995 between the ACW effluent and influent concentrations

996
 997 Table S6: Ordinary least-squares model output for suspended solids & contrast

lm (formula = SSdiff.interp ~ Air_temp + Rainfall + Flow, data = wetland.data)					
Residuals:					
	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-0.052045	-0.010550	-0.000823	0.015973	0.045562
Coefficients:					
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr (> t)	
(Intercept)	1.009	1.757e-02	57.417	<2e-16 ***	
Air_temp	-6.986e-04	1.052e-03	-0.664	0.5156	
Rainfall	-5.755e-03	3.014e-03	-1.909	0.0733	
Flow	-5.502e-05	1.637e-05	-3.362	0.0037 **	
Signif. codes	0 ***	0.001 **	0.01 *	0.05	0.1
Multiple R-squared:	0.4554		Adjusted R-squared: 0.3593		
F-statistic:	4.739 on 3 and 17 DF		p-value: 0.01402		

SS EW-ES: OLS

998

999 Figure S5: Ordinary least squares model graph for suspended solids indicating the modelled difference
 1000 between the ACW effluent and influent concentrations

1001

1002 Table S7: Robust linear model output for suspended solids & contrast

rlm (formula = SSdiff.interp ~ Air_temp + Rainfall + Flow, data = wetland.data)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-0.051946	-0.009336	-0.003394	0.014664	0.047536

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value
(Intercept)	1.0131	0.0175	57.854
Air_temp	-0.0009	0.0010	-0.8650
Rainfall	-0.0057	0.0030	-1.8894
Flow	-0.0001	0.000	-3.5321

Residual standard error: 0.01935 on 17 degrees of freedom

SS EW-ES: RLM

1003

1004 Figure S6: Robust linear model graph for suspended solids indicating the modelled difference between the
 1005 ACW effluent and influent concentrations

1006

1007 Table S8: Ordinary least-squares model output for chemical oxygen demand & contrast

lm (formula = CODdiff.interp ~ Air_temp + Rainfall + Flow, data = wetland.data)					
Residuals:					
	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	0.077394	-0.044558	0.000001	0.000001	0.068759
Coefficients:					
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr (> t)	
(Intercept)	8.390e-01	3.651e-02	22.980	3.06e-14 ***	
Air_temp	5.539e-03	2.186e-03	2.533	0.0214 *	
Rainfall	-1.779e-03	6.264e-03	-0.284	0.7799	
Flow	-6.138e-06	3.401e-05	-0.180	0.8589	
Signif. codes	0 ***	0.001 **	0.01 *	0.05	0.1
Multiple R-squared:	0.2746		Adjusted R-squared: 0.1466		
F-statistic:	2.145 on 3 and 17 DF		p-value: 0.1322		

COD EW-ES: OLS

1008

1009 Figure S7: Ordinary least-squares model graph for chemical oxygen demand indicating the modelled
 1010 difference between the ACW effluent and influent concentrations

1011

1012 Table S9: Robust linear model output for chemical oxygen demand & contrast

rlm (formula = CODdiff.interp ~ Air_temp + Rainfall + Flow, data = wetland.data)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-7.739e-02	-4.456e-02	9.502e-07	4.662e-02	6.876e-02

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value
(Intercept)	0.8390	0.0365	22.9800
Air_temp	0.0055	0.0022	2.5334
Rainfall	-0.0018	0.0063	-0.2839
Flow	0.0000	0.000	-0.1805

Residual standard error: 0.06628 on 17 degrees of freedom

COD EW-ES: RLM

1013
 1014 Figure S8: Regression linear model graph for chemical oxygen demand indicating the modelled difference
 1015 between the ACW effluent and influent concentrations
 1016
 1017 Table S10: Ordinary least-squares model output for total nitrogen & contrast

lm (formula = TNdiff.interp ~ Air_temp + Rainfall + Flow, data = wetland.data)					
Residuals:					
	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-0.24609	-0.02568	0.00356	0.03874	0.23256
Coefficients:					
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr (> t)	
(Intercept)	5.555e-01	7.617e-02	7.292	1.26e-06 ***	
Air_temp	3.590e-03	4.562e-03	0.787	0.44208	
Rainfall	-5.701e-03	1.307e-02	-0.436	0.66815	
Flow	2.991e-04	7.096e-05	4.215	0.000582 ***	
Signif. codes	0 ***	0.001 **	0.01 *	0.05	0.1
Multiple R-squared:	0.5339		Adjusted R-squared: 0.4516		
F-statistic:	6.49 on 3 and 17 DF		p-value: 0.003986		

TN EW-ES: OLS

- 1018
 1019 Figure S9: Ordinary least-squares model graph for total nitrogen indicating the modelled difference
 1020 between the ACW effluent and influent concentrations
 1021
 1022 Table S11: Robust linear model output for total nitrogen

rlm (formula = TNdiff.interp ~ Air_temp + Rainfall + Flow, data = wetland.data)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-0.230137	-0.036122	0.007232	0.024163	0.261321

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value
(Intercept)	0.5682	0.0419	13.5681
Air_temp	0.0011	0.0025	0.4486
Rainfall	-0.0060	0.0072	-0.8414
Flow	0.0003	0.0000	8.2713

Residual standard error: 0.06628 on 17 degrees of freedom

TN EW-ES: RLM

- 1023
- 1024 Figure S10: Robust linear model graph for total nitrogen indicating the modelled difference between the
- 1025 ACW effluent and influent concentrations
- 1026
- 1027 Table S12: Ordinary least-squares model output for ammonium & contrast

lm (formula = NH ₄ diff.interp ~ Air_temp + Rainfall + Flow, data = wetland.data)					
Residuals:					
	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-0.183401	-0.008957	0.019756	0.043528	0.087156
Coefficients:					
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr (> t)	
(Intercept)	1.007e+00	6.105e-02	16.488	6.84e-12 ***	
Air_temp	-1.589e-03	3.656e-03	-0.435	0.669	
Rainfall	-4.669e-03	1.047e-02	-0.446	0.661	
Flow	-5.647e-05	5.687e-05	-0.993	0.335	
Signif. codes	0 ***	0.001 **	0.01 *	0.05	0.1
Multiple R-squared: 0.0724			Adjusted R-squared: -0.09129		
F-statistic: 0.4423 on 3 and 17 DF			p-value: 0.7258		

NH₄-N EW-ES: OLS

1028

1029 Figure S11: Ordinary least-squares model graph for ammonium indicating the modelled difference

1030 between the ACW effluent and influent concentrations

1031

1032 Table S13: Robust linear model output for ammonium & contrast

rlm (formula = NH ₄ diff.interp ~ Air_temp + Rainfall + Flow, data = wetland.data)					
Residuals:					
	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-0.20739	-0.02225	0.01148	0.03639	0.06543
Coefficients:					
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value		
(Intercept)	0.9939	0.0470	21.1358		
Air_temp	0.0000	0.0028	-0.0092		
Rainfall	-0.0059	0.0081	-0.7314		
Flow	0.0000	0.0000	-0.9002		
Residual standard error: 0.05396 on 17 degrees of freedom					

NH₄ N EW-ES: RLM

1033

1034 Figure S12: Robust linear model graph for ammonium indicating the modelled difference between the
1035 ACW effluent and influent concentrations

1036

1037 Table S14: Ordinary least-squares model output for nitrate & contrast

lm (formula = NO ₃ diff.interp ~ Air_temp + Rainfall + Flow, data = wetland.data)					
Residuals:					
	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-37.113	-2.476	0.397	7.000	16.698
Coefficients:					
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr (> t)	
(Intercept)	-30.7593	8.822629	-3.486	0.00283 **	
Air_temp	0.763030	0.528332	1.444	0.16685	
Rainfall	-1.864858	1.513726	-1.232	0.23473	
Flow	0.026431	0.008219	3.216	0.00507 **	
Signif. codes	0 ***	0.001 **	0.01 *	0.05	0.1
Multiple R-squared: 0.4694			Adjusted R-squared: 0.3758		
F-statistic: 5.014 on 3 and 17 DF			p-value: 0.01137		

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1041

1042 Table S15: Robust linear model output for nitrate & contrast

rlm (formula = NO ₃ diff.interp ~ Air_temp + Rainfall + Flow, data = wetland.data)					
Residuals:					
	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-54.73776	-1.70858	-0.01938	1.70612	12.65026
Coefficients:					
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value		
(Intercept)	-13.6298	2.7330	-4.9872		
Air_temp	0.0397	0.1637	0.2424		
Rainfall	-0.3184	0.4689	-0.6791		
Flow	0.0141	0.0025	5.5567		
Residual standard error: 2.533 on 17 degrees of freedom					

1043

1044 Table S16: Ordinary least-squares model output for total phosphorus & contrast

lm (formula = Pdiff.interp ~ Air_temp + Rainfall + Flow, data = wetland.data)					
Residuals:					
	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-0.046745	-0.007525	0.001187	0.013159	0.022936
Coefficients:					
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr (> t)	
(Intercept)	9.629e-01	1.405e-02	68.519	<2e-16 ***	
Air_temp	-3.307e-04	8.415e-04	-0.393	0.699	
Rainfall	-4.439e-04	2.411e-03	-0.184	0.856	
Flow	1.655e-05	1.309e-05	1.264	0.223	
Signif. codes	0 ***	0.001 **	0.01 *	0.05	0.1
Multiple R-squared: 0.1007			Adjusted R-squared: -0.05802		
F-statistic: 0.6344 on 3 and 17 DF			p-value: 0.603		

P EW-ES: OLS

1045
 1046 Figure S13: Ordinary least-squares model graph for total phosphorus indicating the modelled difference
 1047 between the ACW effluent and influent concentrations
 1048
 1049 Table S17: RLM model output for total phosphorus

rlm (formula = Pdiff.interp ~ Air_temp + Rainfall + Flow, data = wetland.data)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-0.0544326	-0.0060075	0.0004999	0.0098416	0.0190727

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value
(Intercept)	0.9550	0.0115	82.7683
Air_temp	-0.0001	0.0007	-0.1019
Rainfall	0.0002	0.0020	0.1155
Flow	0.0000	0.0000	2.4338

Residual standard error: 0.01459 on 17 degrees of freedom

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 1052
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 1054
 1055

P EW-ES: RLM

1056
 1057 Figure S14: RLM model graph for total phosphorus indicating the modelled difference between the ACW
 1058 effluent and influent concentrations

1059
 1060 Figure S15. Trend of synthetic urea price in Eastern Europe from April 2017 until March 2022 and
 1061 calculated cost of ammonium nitrate (AN) solution production over the monitoring period and in March
 1062 2022.